

Table 1. Host plant range of *C. gangis*. IRRI headhouse, Feb-Mar 1990.^a

	Parameter					Overall ranking ^f
	Larval survival (%) ^{b,c}	Larval developmental period (d) ^d	Larval growth index (rating) ^e	Eggs laid (no./female)		
Poaceae						
TN1 rice	79.0 ± 9.5 a	22.1 ± 0.8 a	3.5 ± 0.4 a	46.7 ± 40.7 a		1
<i>Leptochloa chinensis</i> (L.) Nees	73.0 ± 20.0 ab	23.7 ± 1.4 b	3.1 ± 0.9 ab	45.8 ± 12.5 a		2
Maize	69.9 ± 12.0 abc	29.4 ± 0.9 c	2.8 ± 0.5 bc	25.5 ± 18.9 c-g		3
<i>Echinochloa colona</i> (L.) Link	63.0 ± 26.3 abc	30.2 ± 1.6 d	2.4 ± 1.0 cd	34.1 ± 9.3 a-e		4
<i>E. glabrescens</i> Munro ex Hook f.	67.0 ± 18.3 abc	30.6 ± 0.9 e	2.5 ± 0.7 bcd	36.2 ± 7.3 a-d		5
<i>Eleusine indica</i> (L.) Gaertn.	72.0 ± 18.7 ab	31.5 ± 1.8 ef	2.8 ± 0.7 bc	21.5 ± 5.6 d-h		6
<i>Isachne globosa</i> L.	53.0 ± 46.4 c	31.5 ± 1.0 ef	2.0 ± 1.8 de	49.5 ± 38.9 a		7
<i>Paspalum scrobiculatum</i> L.	57.0 ± 22.1 bc	36.1 ± 1.2 fg	1.7 ± 0.7 ef	29.2 ± 15.8 b-f		8
<i>P. conjugatum</i> Berg.	31.3 ± 16.0 d	29.1 ± 1.2 c	1.2 ± 0.6 h	36.7 ± 13.7 a-d		9
<i>Leersia hexandra</i> Sw.	24.1 ± 23.2 de	31.5 ± 1.2 ef	0.9 ± 0.9 ghi	44.7 ± 6.7 ab		12
<i>Brachlaria mutica</i> (Forsk.) Stapf.	15.0 ± 7.1 def	37.7 ± 0.9 gh	0.4 ± 0.2 ij	17.7 ± 7.1 e-h		13
<i>B. distachya</i> (L.) Stapf.	12.1 ± 11.4 ef	38.1 ± 1.4 gh	0.4 ± 0.3 ij	16.2 ± 12.5 fgh		14
<i>Chloris barbata</i> Sw.	10.0 ± 0.0 ef	38.1 ± 1.2 gh	0.2 ± 0.0 j	17.8 ± 1.7 e-h		15
<i>Imperata cylindrica</i> (L.) Beauv	8.0 ± 4.2 ef	42.1 ± 1.6 i	0.2 ± 0.0 j	6.1 ± 6.0 h		18
Cyperaceae						
<i>Cyperus kyllingia</i> Endl.	57.2 ± 24.5 bc	32.0 ± 1.6 f	1.7 ± 0.8 ef	38.3 ± 11.7 abc		10
<i>C. brevifolius</i> (Rottb.) Hassk.	52.1 ± 24.4 c	38.1 ± 1.2 gh	1.5 ± 0.7 efg	15.9 ± 4.6 fgh		11
<i>Fimbristylis miliacea</i> (L.)	19.0 ± 8.8 def	35.6 ± 0.7 fg	0.6 ± 0.3 h-j	11.7 ± 4.4 gh		13
<i>Cyperus iria</i> L.	22.0 ± 9.2 def	43.0 ± 0.7 i	0.6 ± 0.2 h-j	33.2 ± 11.9 a-e		16
<i>C. rotundus</i> L.	4.0 ± 5.2 f	39.6 ± 1.1 h	0.1 ± 0.0 j	22.8 ± 6.3 c-g		17
Commelinaceae						
<i>Commelina diffusa</i> Burm. f.	4.0 ± 5.2 f	30.8 ± 0.7 e	0.1 ± 0.0 i	25.3 ± 7.0 c-g		19

^aAv of 10 replications. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different (P < 0.01) by LSD statistical test.

^bSurvival (%) = $\frac{\text{Larvae becoming pupae}}{\text{Total larvae}} \times 100$. ^cn = 100. ^dn = 10. ^eGrowth index = $\frac{\text{Larval survival (\%)}}{\text{Larval growth period (d)}}$. ^f1 = best, 19 = worst.

Table 2. Life history of *C. gangis*. IRRI headhouse, Mar-Dec 1989.^a

	$\bar{x} \pm$ SD
Egg incubation period (d)	4.6 ± 0.8
Larval stadium (d)	
I	4.5 ± 0.5
II	4.9 ± 1.3
III	4.0 ± 0.7
IV	4.7 ± 0.8
V	4.0 ± 0.5
Prepupa (d)	2.0 ± 0
Pupa (d)	8.5 ± 0.5
Total developmental period (d)	37.2 ± 1.4
Moth longevity (d)	12.0 ± 1.5
Eggs laid (no./female)	46.7 ± 40.7

^an = 100.

Highest larval survival to pupation (n = 100) occurred on rice (79%), *Leptochloa chinensis* (73%), and *Eleusine indica* (72%). The quickest larval developmental period was on rice (22.1 d), although on all other plant hosts development was significantly delayed. These two developmental parameters resulted in a high growth index for rice (3.5) and *L. chinensis* (3.1), which were significantly higher than for the other plants. Rice (TN1) was

the most suitable host (Table 1).

All the plant species served as ovipositional hosts and supported complete development of *C. gangis*. Greatest fecundity (no. eggs/female) occurred from moths reared on *Isachne globosa* (49.5), rice (46.7), *L. chinensis* (45.8), *Leersia hexandra* (44.7), *Cyperus kyllingia* (38.3), *Paspalum conjugatum*

(36.7), *E. glabrescens* (36.2), and *E. colona* (34.1) (Table 1).

Life history data for *C. gangis* developing on rice appear in Table 2.

Even though *C. gangis* is highly adapted to rice, it occurs rarely and has never been reported to be economically important. ■

Shifts in population characteristics of brown planthopper (BPH) immigrants to Japan

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Hopperburn was observed for the first time on a BPH-resistant breeding line with *Bph 1* gene in Japan in 1990, indicating that BPH immigrating to Japan may have changed significantly. This population shift was evaluated

quantitatively using 96 immigrants in 1992.

Honeydew excretion of adult females was measured individually. Insects were confined to leaf sheaths of rice at the early tillering stage with clip-on Parafilm sachets (about 1.5 × 1.5 cm) at 25 °C for 1 d. The same insects were transferred daily from resistant IR26 (*Bph 1* gene) to susceptible japonica Reihou to resistant IR42 (*bph 2* gene) to clarify the biotypic properties of individual females.

Individuals excreting at least 10 mg honeydew were tentatively classified as able to feed normally. Of the 92% that

Honeydew excreted (mg)

Individuals (no.)

Honeydew excreted by 96 adult female immigrants on Reihou, IR26, and IR42. Individuals were arranged in descending order based on amounts of honeydew excreted on Reihou. Japan, 1992.

fed normally on Reihou, 47% could feed on IR26, and 1% could feed on IR26, IR42, and Reihou. Average honeydew excreted daily was about 46 ± 23 mg on Reihou and 33 ± 18 mg on IR26, respectively. Only one female excreted 49 mg on IR42. Five females excreted

more than 10 mg on IR26, but less than 10 mg on Reihou and IR42 (see figure).

We conclude that about half of the recent BPH immigrants to Japan were biotype 2, and the rest were still biotype 1. ■

Detoxifying enzymes of the brown planthopper (BPH)

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Among the major detoxifying enzymes, hydrolases are the most studied group because of their involvement in the resistance of *Nilaparvata lugens* Stål to both organophosphorus and pyrethroid insecticides. Activity of carboxylesterase toward 1-naphthyl acetate in BPH is at least 20-fold higher than in some lepidoptera. More than a dozen carboxylesterase isozymes have been resolved using isoelectric-focusing electrophoresis, and substrate specificity has been observed in some isozymes.

Considerable conjugation of 1-chloro-2,4-dinitrobenzene mediated by glutathione transferase has been observed in BPH. This enzyme in the pest, however, does not show any detectable activity toward another model substrate, 1,2-dichloro-4-nitrobenzene, or insecticides (parathion, paraoxon, and methyl parathion) known to be substrates

for glutathione transferase in other insects.

Activity of microsomal P450-dependent monooxygenases toward several model substrates in BPH is very low—only about 1/50 to 1/100 of that in some lepidopterous insects. It has been hypothesized that this low monooxygenase activity may be due to its contact with only water-soluble materials in plant saps (see table).

The metabolic mechanisms of insecticide resistance observed in BPH may reflect the fundamental makeup of detoxifying enzymes. A lack of cross-resistance in BPH from existing organophosphorus/pyrethroid resistance (conferred by enhanced carboxylesterase hydrolysis) to buprofezin might be because the carboxylesterases do not hydrolyze this chitin synthesis inhibitor. Further, there may not be active microsomal monooxygenases with which to hydroxylate buprofezin, a known detoxifying reaction observed in soils. If resistance to buprofezin should occur in BPH, it might be the result of target site alterations. ■

Activities of detoxifying enzymes of *Nilaparvata lugens* Stal.

Enzyme and substrate	Specific activity
Carboxylesterase	
1-naphthyl acetate	40.2 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{min}$ per mg protein
2-naphthyl acetate	36.9 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{min}$ per mg protein
Glutathione transferase	
1-chloro-2,4-dinitrobenzene	192 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{min}$ per mg protein
1,2-dichloro-4-nitrobenzene	ND ^a
Parathion	ND
Paraoxon	ND
Methyl parathion	ND
Microsomal P450-monooxygenases	
Aldrin	3.75 pmol/min per mg protein
Methoxyresorufin	2.90 pmol/min per mg protein
Ethoxyresorufin	ND
Ethoxycoumarin	ND

^aND = not detected.

Integrated pest management—other pests

Efficacy of benomyl in controlling the ufra nematode in Vietnam

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We conducted two experiments to test the effect of benomyl on the ufra nematode, *Ditylenchus angustus*, in deepwater rice in farmers' fields.

The first experiment was conducted in the village of Long Thanh My, Thu Duc district, Ho Chi Minh City. The farmer transplanted 45-d-old seedlings of variety Tieu doi in an ufra-prone area. Eight benomyl treatments were evaluated.

The second experiment was conducted, in Dong Phu, Chau Thanh district, Can Tho Province, in a field dry seeded with variety 1960. Rice showed ufra symptoms 40 d after sowing. Two benomyl and water solutions were tested: 0.1 and 0.2% ai sprayed at a rate of 500 liters/ha. An untreated control was the third treatment.

Fields were cultivated following farmers' practices. Experiments were laid out in a randomized complete block design with four replications using 7- $\times$ 7-m plots for the first experiment and 10- $\times$ 10-m plots for the second experiment. In the first experiment, 10 hills/plot were collected at rice crop maturity for nematode analysis. In the second experiment, five crop cuts of 20- $\times$ 20-cm were collected at random from each plot 1 d before, and 10 and 20 d after benomyl treatments. In both experiments, nematodes were extracted from all of the stems collected. Results were analyzed using ANOVA. Means were separated using DMRT.

D. angustus infestation was low in the first experiment, most probably because of late flooding and low water level during the flood. Results indicate,